

High-resolution holographic reconstruction combined with fluorescence microscopy to identify unwanted *Chlorella* sp. cells in *Haematococcus pluvialis* cultures

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Abstract

This study evaluated the performance of HOLODETECT HiRes+FLUOR3, a laboratory instrument designed for detecting and counting small particles or cells in fluids using fluorescence. The test strains were *Haematococcus pluvialis* and *Chlorella sorokiniana* because of their industrial importance in the functional food markets, and because they have been identified growing in co-culture, especially when the goal is to produce *Haematococcus*. Initial trials focused on optimising the operating conditions to ensure accurate and reproducible measurements. The equipment demonstrated a low coefficient of variation (<5%) for all the different determinations. Due to the cell overlap, sample dilution was necessary prior to analysis. A second set of trials aimed to develop models (i) to identify the cell concentration in monocultures and polycultures, and (ii) to determine the relative abundance of the two test strains in the polycultures. In terms of the total number of cells, the system was able to provide results comparable to those obtained using a Neubauer counting chamber. However, the model development step proved to be important, as different modelling approaches led to different results. Some models might overestimate or underestimate the total cell count. Similarly, the system accurately quantifies the relative abundance of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cells in cultures with varying concentration ratios.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, fluorescence microscopy, high resolution holographic reconstruction, culture monitoring, novel sensors, image analysis

1. Introduction

Microalgae production has attracted significant interest across various industries due to the photosynthetic nature of microalgal biomass and its potential applications. Today, several microalgae-based processes have achieved commercial success; for example, phycocyanin from *Arthrospira platensis* and β -carotene from *Dunaliella salina* are commercially available.

Microalgae are mainly produced autotrophically using open bioreactors, with raceway ponds being the most used design. Raceways have been utilized for over 50 years to produce *Arthrospira* and *Dunaliella*, taking advantage of the fact that the growth conditions for these microalgae are unsuitable for most competing species. The former is produced using high concentrations of sodium bicarbonate, with a pH generally around 10 (Villaró-Cos et al., 2024), while the latter is produced using sea salt, as it can grow well in media with a conductivity higher than $150 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ (Colusse et al., 2020). Producing other strains in raceway reactors is challenging because of the appearance of unwanted fast-growing competing strains that can overtake the culture. For example, a metagenomic analysis revealed that *Nitzschia* sp. was the most abundant microalga in an open bioreactor that had been inoculated with *Scenedesmus almeriensis* approximately one month earlier (Villaró et al., 2022). Even reactors inoculated with extremophile strains can be contaminated with an unwanted microalga or with algal predators such as protozoa, rotifers, and ostracods. For example, *Alkalimonas* sp. and *Lentimonas* sp., as well as an unclassified metazoan, have been found in cultures of *Arthrospira platensis* (Villaró et al., 2023).

The appearance of unwanted microorganisms in microalgal cultures has been overlooked in the scientific literature. Despite the presence of algal predators in large cultures being recognized since the 1960s, most of the works published to date have been carried out using laboratory-scale reactors. At the laboratory-scale, the culture conditions can be easily controlled (e.g., by autoclaving the culture medium), and the appearance of competing strains and/or algal predators is not generally a problem.

However, over the last two decades, several microalgae-based processes have been upscaled and the presence of predators and competing microorganisms has become an important challenge for microalgae producers.

Chlorella vulgaris and *Chlorella sorokiniana* are microalgae of industrial importance since they can be used as human food. They are approved as food by the FDA in the US and by EFSA in the EU and there are several products containing *Chlorella* already available on the market. Despite being fast-growing microorganisms, they are not extremophiles so producing them in open systems is challenging. Moreover, because of their high growth rate, *Chlorella* strains can overtake cultures or other strains. For example, the great abundance of *Chlorella* cells in *Haematococcus pluvialis* cultures can prove problematic when the goal is to produce astaxanthin. Other strains, such as *Chlamydomonas reinhardi*, also act as biotic contaminants of *Haematococcus pluvialis* (Yu et al., 2022). Various strategies have been investigated to stop or limit the growth of unwanted microorganisms. For example, pyraclostrobin-based fungicides and the anionic surfactant sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate have been investigated to control fungal contaminants in cultures of *Scenedesmus dimorphus* and *Grasiella* sp., respectively (Ding et al., 2020). Adjusting the pH has also been assessed as a strategy for controlling the growth of unwanted microorganisms in cultures of *Haematococcus pluvialis* (Hwang et al., 2019) and a combination of botanical pesticides was investigated for exterminating rotifers in cultures of *Arthrospira platensis* (Huang et al., 2014).

To implement effective contingency measures and combat unwanted microorganisms, it is crucial to first identify the contaminant. The sooner the contaminant is detected, the greater the chances of controlling its growth. For this reason, it is important to develop and implement online monitoring tools that can detect the appearance of unwanted microorganisms, including microalgae, in industrial cultures. Various strategies are now being studied, including AI-based models, to detect contamination based on spectrophotometry (González-Hernández et al., 2025). In this present work, the authors aimed to evaluate the performance of HOLODETECT HiRes+FLUOR3 (Holodetect

Instruments Ltd., Budapest, Hungary), a laboratory instrument for detecting and counting small particles or cells in fluids using fluorescence. The test strains were *Haematococcus pluvialis* and *Chlorella sorokiniana* because of their industrial importance and because they have both been identified growing in co-culture when the goal was to produce one or the other.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Microalgal cultures

The test strains belonged to the genera *Haematococcus* and *Chlorella*. For *Haematococcus*, the strain used was *Haematococcus pluvialis*, sourced from different culture collections, including 1360B BEA, BMCC 673, Algaria (Italy), SAG 192.80, and CCCryo 096-99. For *Chlorella*, the strain used was *Chlorella sorokiniana*, collected from cultures grown under varied conditions, previously adapted to seawater and cultivated under a range of conditions in a variety of photobioreactor systems, including tubular reactors. The strains were subsequently produced in 1 L controlled bubble columns (pH 8.0; 25 °C) at a constant aeration of 0.2 v/v/min and irradiance of 350 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The culture medium was prepared using 0.90 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ NaNO_3 , 0.14 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ KH_2PO_4 , 0.18 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ MgSO_4 , and 20 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ Karentol[®] Mix Super (Kenogard, Barcelona, Spain), a commercial micronutrient mixture (Morillas-España et al., 2020). The cultures were diluted when needed using fresh culture medium. The biomass concentration was calculated gravimetrically. Briefly, 30 mL of the culture were filtered through pre-dried 0.45 μm filters that were then dried in an oven at 80 °C for 24 h. Before drying, the filters were washed once with 60 mL of distilled water to remove the excess of salts. In addition, the cell density was calculated using a Neubauer counting chamber (NCC) and a Leica DM 750 microscope coupled with a Flexacam i5 camera using Enersight software (Leica Microsistemas, Barcelona, Spain).

2.2 High-resolution holographic reconstruction combined with fluorescence microscopy

The first set of trials aimed to evaluate the performance of the Holodetect HiRes+Fluor3 device in detecting and classifying microalgae cells, and to determine whether sample dilution was required prior to analysis. From now on, HOLODETECT HiRes+FLUOR3 will be referred to as HF3.

The system integrates digital holographic microscopy (DHM), providing a holographic resolution of 600 nm, with multi-wavelength fluorescence microscopy (excitation at 405 nm, 450 nm and 532 nm). In recent years, this combined approach has been explored for microalgae characterization, and enhanced methodologies have been developed which capture both morphological and biochemical features simultaneously (Yourassowsky et al., 2024). Liquid samples were analysed within a flow-through cuvette at a depth of 200 μm and at a rate of 3.6 to 18 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, based on the culture's cell density. The HF3 technology captures the entire 200 μm depth of a sample in a single holographic image, eliminating the need to usual optical refocus and allowing the reconstruction of all objects within a detectable size range of 3 to 75 μm . The flowcell, a rectangular glass slide with a central tube, is used to pass the sample through the system. The slide is arranged in a vertical position, with a silicone tube affixed at both ends, connected to a peristaltic pump. The sample is passed through the flowcell, where two cameras record the information, with the actual view of the sample having to be matched with the fluorescence, thus making it essential to precisely align the holographic and fluorescent channels. Instrument-level parameters, such as camera magnification, rotation, and laser light distribution, must be optimised during the equipment set-up. Slight dynamic offsets can be introduced by operational factors. This is a common challenge in systems that integrate fluorescence and imaging. For instance, the FlowCAM device incorporates a laser in fluorescence triggered mode, which requires calibration of the gain and threshold settings, among others (Chen et al., 2023; Jaffari et al., 2024).

To ensure the accuracy of the HF3 equipment, an automatic calibration routine is performed prior to each use. For this calibration, a sample of the fresh culture is

introduced, allowing the system to automatically calculate and compensate any offset. This ensures the correct overlap between the reconstructed holographic object and its corresponding fluorescence signal.

To determine the appropriate microalgae cell density to allow accurate counting, samples of *Chlorella sorokiniana* and *Haematococcus pluvialis* cultures were analysed using both HF3 and NCC to compare reliability and reproducibility. Each culture was serially diluted until the system could accurately distinguish individual cells, even in cases of partial overlap. At each dilution step, cell density was quantified using both methods, and dry weight measurements were taken. The process was repeated until the cell concentration became too low for a reliable counting threshold using either method.

Furthermore, the minimum number of objects required to achieve reproducible results was determined by modifying the system's 'number of objects to be measured', ranging from 375 to 6000 objects per measurement. Subsequent counts were performed using NCC for comparative analysis.

2.3 Model generation

HF3 employs deep neural networks (DNNs) implemented in PyTorch (v2.2.0 with CUDA 11.8 support) for automated classification (Paszke et al., 2019) and trained using a staged few-shot learning approach (Wang et al., 2023). Three different models were developed in this study. Two of them were trained using monocultures of *Chlorella sorokiniana* and *Haematococcus pluvialis* separately. The use of pure cultures to generate the model ensured accurate cell labelling with this approach, as no other microalgae were present. In these models, to create the database, only the target strain was manually annotated in each case. This resulted in two species-specific models, one for *Chlorella* and the other for *Haematococcus*, in which all non-target particles were labelled as "others". A third model was generated by labelling both strains independently within the same training dataset, allowing direct discrimination between them.

For each model, initial training was performed on small, annotated datasets (approximately ten objects per class). A preliminary model was trained and used to pre-

classify additional detected objects, employing semi-supervised iterations where preliminary model predictions were manually corrected and reintroduced into the training set. This allowed the training database to be expanded and refined. The built-in annotation tool facilitated labelling based on holographic morphology and fluorescence signals. This semi-supervised iterative approach helped to improve classification accuracy while minimising manual labelling effort.

The final annotated datasets were randomly divided into training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) sets, with the only requirement being that each set contain an equal number of elements of each class to avoid bias in the training. The validation set was held out during training to prevent overfitting, with model training automatically stopping when validation accuracy plateaued. The DNN architecture incorporated both holographic and fluorescence data, with inputs standardised to the same size (128 pixels), since the model has a uniform and invariable input size.

2.4 Model validation

Model validation was conducted using pure monocultures of *Chlorella sorokiniana* and *Haematococcus pluvialis* (distinct from the samples used for model training), with cell concentrations accurately determined using the NCC. The use of pure cultures ensured that no unwanted species interfered with the model specificity assessment. From these quantified cultures, six standardised cellular mixtures were prepared at the following volumetric ratios: 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 90%, and 100% for each species. These mixtures were designed to represent a range of contamination levels, from highly contaminated to pure cultures, simulating the contamination scenarios that may be present in microalgae culture systems.

Each prepared mixture was analysed using all three classification models to evaluate their performance under varying species abundance conditions. The number of cells analysed per sample corresponded to the previously established optimal object count to ensure accuracy and reproducibility across replicates. The aim was to evaluate the ability of each model to correctly identify, quantify, and classify both strains across a range of

relative abundances. The model outputs were compared with the expected ratios derived from manual counts. This validation strategy enabled a comprehensive assessment of each model's generalisability and its ability to detect and quantify target strains in mixed cultures.

2.5 Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using a one-way analysis of variance and a Fisher's LSD post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) using Statgraphics Centurion v19 (Statgraphics Technologies Inc., VA, US) software.

3. Results and discussion

As previously highlighted, the presence of unwanted microorganisms, such as microalgae, in *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cultures is a common issue that poses a challenge at the commercial scale. These microorganisms can either present a health risk or compromise the quality of the biomass produced. For instance, in the case of *Haematococcus*, the growth of competing strains can lead to reduced astaxanthin recovery yields. When this occurs, it becomes essential to implement control measures, such as filtration, to eliminate or limit the growth of the undesired strain. The earlier these measures are implemented, the better. Therefore, the adoption of online monitoring tools capable of identifying different strains or microorganisms is crucial. In this study, *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* were used as model organisms, and the HOLODETECT HiRes+FLUOR3 (Holodetect Instruments Ltd., Budapest, Hungary), or HF3, was validated for the first time.

3.1 Equipment calibration

HF3 utilizes digital holographic microscopy and artificial intelligence to detect, classify, and count cells and objects ranging in size from 3 to 75 μm . The primary objectives of the initial study trials were (i) to assess the device's ability to detect and classify cultures with varying cell concentrations, and (ii) to determine the minimum number of reads required to obtain reproducible results.

The first objective is particularly important given that, in concentrated cultures, some cells may overlap, necessitating sample dilution before readings to ensure accurate analysis. This was observed in previous studies where overlapping cells or cell aggregates limited the accuracy of techniques such as flow cytometry, plate counting, or electron microscopy (Di Caprio, 2020). Cultures containing different concentrations of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* were analysed using both HF3 and NCC. The results are shown in Figure 1. For the *Chlorella* strains, a positive correlation was observed between the cell density assessed using HF3 and NCC ($p < 0.05$; 0.9773). The biomass concentration ranged between 0.00 and 0.06 g·L⁻¹; higher concentrations led to cell overlapping and to larger differences between the two counting methods. In turn, *Haematococcus* cells could be counted at higher concentrations using HF3, observing minor differences between the results obtained using HF3 and NCC at a concentration of approximately 1 g·L⁻¹. In this case, a positive correlation was observed between the cell density calculated using HF3 and NCC in cultures with biomass concentrations ranging from 0.0 to 1.1 g·L⁻¹ ($p < 0.05$; 0.9889). Despite the biomass concentration on a dry weight basis being much higher, the cell density in both cultures was of the same order of magnitude. The reason for this is the size of the cells: while the diameter of *Chlorella* is around 2-5 µm, the diameter of *Haematococcus* cells is in the 10-60 µm range (Baroni et al., 2019). The need to reduce the concentration also occurs in other cell counting methods. Similarly, in a previous study, the authors reported greater noise in the data computed from images of a flow-through microscope at the end of the growth phase (50-60 cells per image) than at the beginning (below 10 cells per image). In that study, the authors filtered the data using a 12-h asymmetric median to obtain a smoother output (Havlik et al., 2013). Overall, cell density influenced the accuracy of the results ($p < 0.05$). For concentrated cultures, a dilution step might be necessary to correctly estimate biomass concentration and identify contaminants. These results are in line with those observed in systems such as FlowCam. When operating at high cell densities in FlowCam, overlapping has been observed, which can lead to errors of up to 14.8% when

compared to traditional microscopy methods (Álvarez et al., 2011). The dilution step might not be necessary for larger microalgae such as *Haematococcus pluvialis*, where the system was able to accurately calculate the cell density at a concentration higher than $1 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$.

The second objective of these initial trials was to determine the minimum number of read objects needed to achieve accurate and reproducible results. To accomplish this, multiple measurements of the same sample were taken under consistent conditions, with a varying number of objects read for each sample (ranging from 375 to 6000). The results are shown in Figure 2. Overall, no differences were observed in the CV values obtained for both genera, being below 5% in all the analysed samples. However, the number of read objects had an impact on the CV, which decreased from 2.3 to 0.3 in *Chlorella* cultures when 375 and 6000 objects were read, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the CV decreased from 3.9 to 1.9 in *Haematococcus* cultures when 375 and 6000 objects were read, respectively ($p < 0.05$). For both strains, no differences were observed between the CV obtained when measuring 1500 objects or more, suggesting that measuring 1500 objects per sample is enough to achieve reproducible results. Even if a lower number of objects is counted, the maximum CV value obtained was below 5%. The number of objects analysed per sample is important because the higher this value, the lower the statistical error reduction factor, which is relevant in biological processes where higher cell concentrations result in reduced effects. The accuracy of the results was also calculated comparing the number of objects read using HF3 and NCC. Overall, the larger the number of objects analysed, the lower the discrepancy between the results obtained using HF3 and NCC. The same occurred when using both *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* strains. When just 375 objects were analysed per sample, the discrepancy between the data obtained using HF3 was in the 15-20% range and decreased to around 10% when 6000 objects per sample were analysed ($p < 0.05$). It is important to highlight that all the methods used to determine cell density, including the use of NCC, have an error and

therefore the observed discrepancy between the results does not necessarily mean that the results are incorrect.

These first trials demonstrated that the higher the number of objects detected, the greater the reproducibility of the results and the lower the discrepancy between HF3 and NCC. However, no improvements were observed between measuring 1500 and 6000 objects. Regardless of the number of objects analysed, the CV was below 5% in all the samples, indicating very high precision and reproducibility. Nonetheless, one limitation identified was the need to dilute the *Chlorella* cultures since cell densities higher than $2 \cdot 10^6$ cells·mL⁻¹ led to lower accuracy; this is because cells overlap making it a challenge for the software to identify individual cells. This same problem was highlighted by researchers comparing different methods for measuring biomass concentrations in microalgae cultures (Sarrafzadeh et al., 2015). In the case of *Chlorella*, a cell density of $2 \cdot 3 \cdot 10^6$ cells·mL⁻¹ represents a biomass concentration of approximately 0.04-0.06 g·L⁻¹, which can be easily achieved in laboratory-scale photobioreactors and in large-scale systems alike. Therefore, to use HF3 as an online monitoring system in large-scale systems, an automatic dilution step might be needed depending on the strain being produced. It has been demonstrated that the HF3 system has the capacity to distinguish between different microalgae species by training with specific species image libraries. The system can be adapted to identify different species under varying conditions, provided that the morphological characteristics are sufficiently distinctive and adequate training data are available.

3.2 Model development

Two different strategies were followed: (i) developing a model for each strain and (ii) developing a model where both strains were considered. When developing a model for each strain, the objects counted as “others” were mainly cells (in the *Haematococcus* model) and *Haematococcus* (in the *Chlorella* model). The model developed using just *Chlorella* cells was named M1. M2 refers to the model where only *Haematococcus* cells were labelled and M3 refers to the model where both strains were considered

independently within the same dataset. The first strategy, which involved developing separate models for each strain, was based on the hypothesis that a model focused on a single species would enhance the sensitivity to detect the target organism while minimising potential particle noise classification. Conversely, the second strategy hypothesised that integrating both species into one model would yield greater robustness in complex environments with mixed species.

The imaging system used generates two complementary types of data for each field of view. As shown in Figure 3, the left-hand image is a holographic reconstruction, while the right-hand image displays the fluorescence signals emitted by the sample. Model M1, as illustrated in Figure 3A, tended to overestimate the number of *Chlorella* cells, mainly because it misclassified noncellular particles and environmental debris as target cells. This limitation was largely attributed to the model's reliance on chlorophyll autofluorescence signals, particularly the red fluorescence ('FLUOR_INTENSITY_RED') emitted, which is known to be susceptible to interference by external fluorescence sources and particulate matter. As previously reported, the red fluorescence channel cannot clearly distinguish between chlorophyll signals and other fluorescent emissions, making a precise classification difficult (Takahashi, 2019). The model also relied on morphological parameters, including area and perimeter ('MASK_AREA' and 'MASK_PERIMETER'), focussing on the photosynthetic pigment profile and cell dimensions characteristic of *Chlorella sorokiniana*.

In contrast, the M2 model, developed using pure *Haematococcus* cultures, showed improved specificity in detecting *Haematococcus* cells, due to the significant difference in size. The model was trained with samples containing all the physiological phases of *Haematococcus pluvialis*, including motile and vegetative green cells, and non-motile red cells. Recognising different sizes of *Haematococcus* cells across their phases, with non-motile cells typically 10-50 μm and motile cells 5-30 μm (Zhang et al., 2017), the model incorporated a size-based filter. The filter used MASK_MINENCCIRCDIAMETER (36.13 \pm 30.92 μm), which allowed the model to effectively exclude small particles and

contaminants, such as *Chlorella* (with a cell size less than 5 μm), from being misclassified as *Haematococcus*. Despite the improvement, there were still challenges in distinguishing between aggregates of small cells such as *Chlorella* and individual *Haematococcus* cells, as can be seen in Figure 3B. This highlighted that, while size filtering improved specificity, it was not sufficient to distinguish all the cells in a contaminated culture.

The third model, M3, was developed to address the limitations observed in the first strategy. This was achieved by considering both *Chlorella sorokiniana* and *Haematococcus pluvialis* as independent classes during model training. This integrated model took advantage of multiple fluorescence channels ('FLUOR_INTENSITY_RED' and 'FLUOR_2/3') in combination with a wider range of morphological descriptors to achieve a more refined discrimination between target cells and environmental noise. The integration of fluorescence profiles with detailed morphological parameters was shown to yield superior results in the case of M3.

Comparative analysis demonstrated that M1 achieved high sensitivity for *Chlorella* but was prone to false positives, particularly in contaminated samples, due to its reliance on fluorescence intensity. This overestimation accords with well-documented challenges faced in imaging-based cell counting systems, such as imaging cytometers (e.g., FlowCam) operating in auto-image mode (Dashkova et al., 2017). In contrast, M2 provided greater specificity for *Haematococcus* by focussing on size and circularity parameters. Nevertheless, it struggled to distinguish aggregates from single cells. M3 outperformed both M1 and M2 by integrating fluorescence and morphological features, dynamically balancing parameter weighting to maintain precise classification across varying conditions, effectively reducing overestimation and improving accuracy, as shown in Figure 3C. In contrast, and in line with findings from fluorescence-enhanced cytometry (Álvarez et al., 2014; Garmendia et al., 2013; Owen et al., 2022), we observed that the combination of multiple fluorescence channels with a higher number of morphological parameters in our M3 model substantially improved counting accuracy.

Operational benchmarking showed that M1 and M2 offered faster processing times (averaging 14.44 ± 1.41 ms per image), while M3 required slightly longer (19.65 ± 1.57 ms per image) due to its more complex multiclass framework. Nonetheless, the additional computational load was justified by its superior accuracy. These findings highlight critical trade-offs between model specialisation and generalisation.

3.3 Validation

The developed models (M1, M2, and M3) described in the previous section were validated using different cultures that contained varying concentrations of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cells. HF3 calculated the total cellular density in each case as well as the percentage of cells labelled as either *Chlorella* or *Haematococcus*. The results from the model validations are shown in Figure 4. Figures 4A and 4G show the accuracy of the three models in quantifying microalgal cells in a culture containing only *Chlorella* or *Haematococcus*, while Figures 4B-F show the accuracy of the different models in quantifying microalgal cells in a polyculture containing *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cells at different cell concentrations. When examining cultures containing only *Chlorella* or *Haematococcus* cells, all three models gave results comparable to those of NCC. However, when the cultures consisted of a mixture of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cells, the cell count was model-dependent ($p < 0.05$). Overall, model M1 overestimated the total number of cells, especially in the cultures with a higher concentration of *Haematococcus* cells ($p < 0.05$). For example, the deviation between the results obtained using HF3 and NCC was around 100% in the culture containing 10% *Chlorella* and 90% *Haematococcus* and decreased to around 10% in the culture containing 90% *Chlorella* and 10% *Haematococcus* ($p < 0.05$). Still, this value was higher than that expected for a model developed using *Chlorella* cells. In addition, the M1 model identified small particles with no fluorescence as *Chlorella* (Figure 3) contributing to an overestimate of the total cell count. In turn, model M2 accurately quantified the total number of cells similar to NCC. As *Haematococcus* cells are larger, the model did not identify small particles as cells, like in M1. No major differences were observed between the two methods (M2 and

NCC) presenting a deviation below 10% for all the different cultures studied. Model M3 permitted accurate cell quantification compared to NCC, independently of the culture used. No differences were observed in the cell count when using M3 and HF3, regardless of the culture used. Table 1 shows the accuracy of M1-M3 in quantifying the abundance of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* in the different cultures. Overall, the models were able to identify the presence of the different strains, and which strain was predominant in each culture. M1, the model developed using *Chlorella* cultures, presented greater accuracy in the cultures where *Chlorella* cells predominated. The deviation between the *Chlorella* concentration using HF3 and NCC was ~5 and ~7% in cultures where *Chlorella* cells represented 75 and 90% of the cells, respectively. In turn, when just 10% of the cells belonged to the *Chlorella* genus, the HF3 system recognised 58.8% of the cells as *Chlorella*. As mentioned above, the system recognised some particles with no fluorescence as *Chlorella* cells along with some *Haematococcus* cells as groups of *Chlorella* cells. The same error was observed when analysing the culture using M2. This model, which was developed using cultures of *Haematococcus* only, recognised that the culture containing 10% *Chlorella* cells was made up of *Haematococcus* cells (56.5%) and other objects, including *Chlorella* (43.5%). This problem was resolved when analysing the cultures using M3, the model developed using both *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cultures. In this case, the deviation between the results obtained using HF3 and NCC was minimal, and the results presented a positive correlation for both the *Chlorella* ($p < 0.05$; 0.9791) and *Haematococcus* ($p < 0.05$; 0.9790) cultures. Model M3 proved to be accurate, especially when monocultures were analysed, identifying 99.9% of the *Chlorella* cells and 95.9% of the *Haematococcus* cells in the *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* monocultures, respectively.

The validation results presented above highlight the HF3 system's strengths in identifying and quantifying microalgae in monocultures and polycultures. This shows that the HF3 system is a valuable alternative to other image-based systems, such as FlowCam. FlowCam relies on two-dimensional imaging, fluorescence triggering and flow cytometry

(Otálora et al., 2023), which can limit its effectiveness in dense cultures or when distinguishing between morphologically similar species. In contrast, HF3 combines high-resolution digital holography with fluorescence. Although HF3 needs sample dilution for small cells at high densities and takes slightly longer to process complex models, its accuracy and flexibility make it a strong contender for monitoring microalgae.

Conclusions

High-resolution holographic reconstruction combined with fluorescence microscopy was used to calculate the cellular concentration of monocultures and polycultures of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus*. This technology permitted accurate cell quantification in cultures of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* and allowed one to quantify the abundance of each genus independently. Three models were developed. The latter, where the two genera were considered independently, provided the best results, allowing one to quantify the abundance of each genus and the cell density rapidly and to obtain results comparable to those of a Neubauer counting chamber. The main limitation in *Chlorella* cultures was the need for dilution, as high cell densities led to inaccurate results. Future work will focus on developing novel models that include different strains, thus allowing one to fully characterize cultures containing more than two strains.

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Conflict of interests

Barbara Bicsák was employed by Holodetect Instruments Ltd. (Budapest, Hungary) during the experiments. The other authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available by the corresponding author on request.

CRedit author statement

Salinas-García, M: Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft;
Bicsák, B.: Investigation; *Lafarga, T.*: Formal analysis, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft; *Ación, G.*: Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Table 1. Model validation: Abundance of *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus* cells in monocultures and polycultures. The results are the average of five independent determinations \pm SD.

Culture*	M1		M2		M3	
	<i>Chlorella</i> (%)	<i>Others</i> (%)	<i>Others</i> (%)	<i>Haematococcus</i> (%)	<i>Chlorella</i> (%)	<i>Haematococcus</i> (%)
100%C	89.3 \pm 1.9	10.6 \pm 1.9	99.9 \pm 0.0	0.1 \pm 0.0	99.9 \pm 0.0	0.0 \pm 0.0
90%C-10%H	82.5 \pm 1.3	17.5 \pm 1.3	91.1 \pm 1.3	8.9 \pm 1.3	89.0 \pm 3.9	10.9 \pm 3.9
75%C-25%H	70.7 \pm 1.2	29.3 \pm 1.2	78.5 \pm 1.3	21.5 \pm 1.3	66.5 \pm 1.7	33.5 \pm 1.7
50%C-50%H	64.9 \pm 1.5	35.1 \pm 1.5	66.9 \pm 2.1	33.1 \pm 2.1	40.9 \pm 1.8	59.1 \pm 1.8
25%C-75%H	58.9 \pm 2.5	41.1 \pm 2.5	48.3 \pm 2.3	51.7 \pm 2.3	13.6 \pm 1.4	86.4 \pm 1.4
10%C-90%H	58.83 \pm 1.5	41.2 \pm 1.5	43.5 \pm 3.8	56.5 \pm 3.8	8.7 \pm 1.3	91.3 \pm 1.3
100%H	25.6 \pm 6.4	73.2 \pm 5.6	38.9 \pm 0.0	61.1 \pm 8.4	4.1 \pm 2.9	95.9 \pm 2.9

* C and H refer to *Chlorella* and *Haematococcus*, respectively. The different percentages represent the abundance of cells of each strain.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Effect of the biomass concentration on the performance of HF3 when analysing cultures of (A) *Chlorella* and (B) *Haematococcus*. HF3 and NCC refer to HOLODETECT HiRes+FLUOR3 and Neubauer counting chamber, respectively. The results are the average of five independent determinations per strain \pm SD.

Figure 2. Effect of the number of objects identified on the discrepancy between the HF3 results and a Neubauer counting chamber, the coefficient of variation (CV) and the statistical error reduction factor (SERF) in cultures of (A) *Chlorella* and (B) *Haematococcus*. Values represent the mean value of five independent determinations \pm SD.

Figure 3. Identification of strains when developing (A) M1, (B) M2, and (C) M3 using a culture containing 90% *Haematococcus* and 10% *Chlorella* cells.

Figure 4. Cell count in cultures of (A) 100% *Chlorella* cells, (B) 90% *Chlorella* and 10% *Haematococcus* cells, (C) 75% *Chlorella* and 25% *Haematococcus* cells, (D) 50% *Chlorella* and 50% *Haematococcus* cells, (E) 25% *Chlorella* and 75% *Haematococcus* cells, (F) 10% *Chlorella* and 90% *Haematococcus* cells, and (G) 100% *Haematococcus* cells. HF3 and NCC refer to HOLODETECT HiRes+FLUOR3 and Neubauer counting chamber, respectively. The results are the average of five independent determinations \pm SD.

Figure 1

A)

B)

Figure 2

(A)

(B)

Figure 3

A)

B)

C)

Figure 4

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